

INTERNATIONAL CONFERENCE

“Towards a State Plane Coordinate System: Scientific Approaches and Practical Challenges”

<https://www.scrsproject.mk/p/international-conference.html>

Skopje – October 31, 2025

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.17703323

CONFERENCE PROGRAM

8.30-9.30	Registration	<i>Conference classroom B102 – LOCATION in Google Map</i>
9.30-11	Opening of conference & first session Moderators: Bashkim Idrizi, <i>North Macedonia</i> Chryssy Potsiou, <i>Greece</i> Nikola Ribaroski, <i>North Macedonia</i>	Official opening of conference (9.30-9.40) - Bekim Fetaji, Rector of the “Mother Teresa” University – Skopje Welcome speeches (9.40-10): - Diane Dumashie, President of the <i>International Federation of Surveyors - FIG</i> - Georg Gartner, President of the <i>International Cartographic Association - ICA</i> - Nikos Zacharias, President of the <i>European Group of Surveyors</i> - Subija Izeiroski, President of the <i>Geo-SEE Institute</i> - Nikola Ribaroski, President of <i>Chamber of surveyors</i> - Lyubka Pashova, <i>Vice chair of conference</i> Presentation of General sponsor (10-10.15): - Geo Sensors, <i>Celestina Roshniku</i> - FARO, <i>Michaela Ragossnig</i> Scientific/professional presentations (10.15-11): 1. Standard parallels choice for Lambert conformal conic projection for Bulgaria - BGS2005 <i>Temenoujka Bandrova</i> 2. State Map Projection in Croatia <i>Miljenko Lapaine</i> 3. Coordinate Systems and Map Projections Used in Mapping and GIS Activities in Turkey <i>Ibrahim Öztuğ Bildirici</i>
11-11.30	Coffee break	
11.30-13	Second session Moderators: Hrvoje Matijevic, <i>Croatia</i>	1. Some key facts for the realization of a modern National Geodetic Reference System/Frame: The Hellenic case <i>Dimitrios Ampatzidis, Alexandros Konstantinidis, Konstantinos Papatheodorou</i>

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Teuta Jusufi Zenku, *North Macedonia*
Jochem Lesparre, *Netherlands*

2. Challenges and Harmonization of Local Datum Transformations within the Coordinate Reference Systems of North Macedonia

Zoran Cvetkovski, Nikola Ribaroski

3. UAV LiDAR and GNSS Surveys for High-Accuracy Spatial Data Acquisition Case Studies from Croatia and Bosnia and Herzegovina

Nikola Kranjčić, Vlado Cetl, Hrvoje Matijević, Danko Markovinović

4. The role of coordinates in Border Diplomacy: The case of Albania

Anduel Cauli, Pal Nikolli, Oltion Pupi

5. Geodetic Reference Systems and Map Projections in Bulgaria: Historical Context and Modern Applications

Lyubka Pashova

13-13.45 Lunch break

13.45 – 15 Third session

Moderators:

Celestina Roshniku, Albania

Subija Izeiroski, North Macedonia

Lyubka Pashova, Bulgaria

1. From EPSG 2462 to EPSG 6870: The evolution of coordinate systems in Albania

Pal Nikolli, Sonila Sinjari, Xhulia Bygjymi, Denisa Kukajc

2. Making a new CRS inside Europe: practical considerations

Javier Jimenez Shaw

3. Assessment of the Kosova National Coordinate System (KOSOVAREF01) and Evaluation of Alternative Options

Fitore Bajrami Lubishtani, Milot Lubishtani, Pal Nikolli, Bashkim Idrizi

4. Modernised transformation between the Dutch century old national CRS and ETRS89

Jochem Lesparre, Lennard Huisman

5. State plane coordinate systems of North Macedonia

Bashkim Idrizi

15-15.30 Closing session

Moderators:

Nikos Zacharias, Greece

Vlado Cetl, Croatia

Murat Hoxha, Kosova

Pannel discussion:

Temenoujka Bandrova, President of Bulgarian Cartographic Association

Javier Jimenez Shaw, Member of Project Steering Committee of PROJ

İbrahim Öztuğ Bildirici, Expert on map projections

Bashkim Idrizi, Head of project SPCRS-RNM and TSPCS conference chair

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SCIENTIFIC COMMITTEE: Bashkim Idrizi (*Chair, North Macedonia*), Lyubka Pashova (*Co-chair, Bulgaria*), Georg Gartner (*Austria*), Temenoujka Bandrova (*Bulgaria*), Miljenko Lapaine (*Croatia*), Chryssy Potsiou (*Greece*), Bekim Fetaji (*North Macedonia*), Pal Nikolli (*Albania*), Fitore Bajrami Lubishtani (*Kosovo*), Ibrahim Oztug Bildirici (*Turkiye*), Danko Markovinovic (*Croatia*), Vlado Cetl (*Croatia*), Ismail Kabashi (*Austria*), Veton Hamza (*Slovenia*), Michael Gastner (*Singapore*), Sagi Dalyot (*Israel*), Hartmut Mueller (*Germany*), Slobodanka Kljucanin (*Bosnia and Hercegovina*), Fisnik Loshi (*Kosovo*), Subija Izeiroski (*North Macedonia*).

ORGANIZER: [South-East European Research Institute on Geo Sciences](#)

UNDER THE UMBRELLA OF: [International Federation of Surveyors](#)

VENUE/HOST: [University "Mother Teresa" - Skopje](#)

CO-ORGANIZERS:

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